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2 **Multi-Year Evaluation of Stabilized Ammonium Fertilization Strategy:**
3 **Yield Performance of Bread Wheat Varieties and Environmental**
4 **Footprint Assessment**

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14 **Abstract**

15 Nitrate-based and ammonium-based fertilizers are widely used in agriculture, with global nitrogen
16 fertilizer consumption reaching 108 million metric tons in 2022. Wheat, a major global crop,
17 accounts for 18% of total fertilizer use, yet its nitrogen use efficiency is low, leading to significant
18 nitrogen losses. These losses, occurring through ammonia volatilization, nitrate leaching, and
19 nitrous oxide emissions, contribute to climate change, eutrophication, and soil degradation.
20 Stabilized ammonium fertilizers have shown promise in reducing nitrogen losses and greenhouse
21 gas emissions by keeping nitrogen in a stable ammonium form. This study was conducted over
22 three years to assess the effectiveness of stabilized ammonium fertilization (AS) in wheat
23 production, evaluating yield, nitrate losses, and fungal community shifts under selected nitrate
24 and ammonium-based fertilization strategies. Stabilized ammonium fertilization combined with
25 wheat varieties showed varying yield patterns according to the climate, with the most stable grain
26 production in an intermediate climate year. Regardless of climate, this fertilization strategy
27 reduced soil nitrate losses while maintaining ammonium availability and appeared to significantly
28 increase the diversity and abundance of root-associated fungi during wheat flowering in the
29 intermediate climate year. This study integrated agronomic performance and environmental
30 impact assessments of AS fertilization on bread wheat, demonstrating its potential for
31 sustainable integration into wheat production systems.

32 **Keywords**

33 Stabilized ammonium fertilizers, bread wheat, ammonium uptake, yields, nitrate leaching, soil
34 and root-associated fungal communities

35 **Highlights**

- 36 • Over 3 years of field experiments across varying climatic conditions, stabilized NH_4^+
37 fertilization combined with wheat varieties exhibited varying yield patterns, with yields
38 being most favorable in an intermediate climate year.

- 39 • Stabilized NH_4^+ fertilization reduced soil NO_3^- losses independently of climate, while
40 maintaining soil NH_4^+ availability.
- 41 • Monitoring the root-associated fungi in the field during the intermediate year revealed that
42 stabilized NH_4^+ fertilization significantly increases their alpha diversity and richness.

43 1. Introduction

44 Nitrate- and ammonium-based fertilizers, such as calcium nitrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$), urea ($\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2$),
45 anhydrous ammonia (NH_3), ammonium sulfate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$), and ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3), are
46 the commonly utilized nitrogen sources in agriculture (Tufail et al., 2024). In 2022, global
47 consumption of nitrogen fertilizers was approximately 108 million metric tons, largely dominated
48 by urea (around 54 million metric tons), then ammonium nitrate and ammonium sulfate represent
49 5.7 and 4.1 million metric tons, respectively (Statista Search Department, 2024). Wheat ranks
50 amongst the top three crops, with a global production of approximately 780 million tons
51 worldwide (FAOSTAT, 2024). Fertilizer use for wheat production represents 18% of total fertilizer
52 applied globally in agriculture and serves as the primary source of nitrogen. However, its nitrogen
53 use efficiency (NUE) is relatively low, with an estimated 48% of the applied nitrogen fertilizer being
54 absorbed and converted into biomass. The relatively low NUE results in substantial nitrogen
55 losses to the environment (Ladha et al., 2016).

56 Essentially, nitrogen contained in synthetic fertilizers can be lost through release in the
57 atmosphere as well as marine and terrestrial systems (Cassman et al., 2002; Ladha et al., 2005).
58 This environmental pollution fuels greenhouse gas (GHG)-driven climate change, eutrophication,
59 soil acidification, loss of biodiversity and ecosystems functioning, groundwater and air pollution
60 (Vitousek et al., 1997; Fowler et al., 2013; Coskun et al., 2017). Major losses occur through
61 gaseous emissions of ammonia (NH_3) and nitrous oxide (N_2O), as well as nitrate (NO_3^-) leaching.
62 Of particular concern is the release of N_2O , a greenhouse gas with a global warming potential
63 approximately 300 times that of CO_2 , which also contributes to stratospheric ozone depletion

64 (Galloway et al., 2008; Erisman et al., 2011). The chemical reactions leading to nitrogen losses are
65 influenced by factors such as fertilizer application, pH, moisture, and temperature (Chen et al.,
66 2015). Nitrification, a microbial process, converts NH_4^+ into NO_3^- via intermediate nitrite (NO_2^-),
67 primarily mediated by ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) and nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB)
68 (Kowalchuk et al., 2001; Daims et al., 2016). Ammonia-oxidizing archaea (AOA) also contribute to
69 nitrification, particularly in acidic soils, while some *Nitrospira* species can perform complete
70 oxidation (commamox). The great majority of applied nitrogen is lost due to nitrification, followed
71 by NO_3^- leaching and runoff (Subbarao et al., 2015). Denitrification, carried out by bacteria,
72 archaea, and fungi, reduces NO_3^- to nitrogen gases (NO , N_2O , and N_2), contributing further to
73 nitrogen loss (Hayatsu et al., 2008; Aldossari et al., 2021).

74 Among the various strategies to reduce agricultural nitrogen losses, stabilized NH_4^+ fertilizers,
75 which refers to a mixture of NH_4^+ -based fertilizers and nitrification inhibitors, have proven
76 effective in minimizing both NO_3^- leaching and greenhouse gas emissions. By inhibiting the
77 microbial conversion of NH_4^+ to NO_3^- , these compounds help retain nitrogen in a more stable
78 form, reducing its loss through leaching and denitrification (Beeckman et al., 2024). Furthermore,
79 since NH_4^+ does not contribute to N_2O emissions, preserving nitrogen in this form can also help
80 mitigate greenhouse gas release (Subbarao et al., 2021). This strategy has been successfully
81 applied in numerous studies, including field research on wheat (Weiske et al., 2001; Arregui and
82 Quemada 2008; Bozal-Leorri et al., 2022). However, a large-scale experiment encompassing a
83 diverse set of varieties has yet to be conducted.

84 Plant species vary widely in their tolerance to NH_4^+ , with some preferring it as a nitrogen source
85 while others are highly sensitive. Although NH_4^+ is essential for plant nutrition, excessive
86 accumulation can be toxic, with tolerance levels depending on species and concentration (Britto
87 and Kronzucker, 2002). The risk of toxicity is particularly high when NH_4^+ is the sole nitrogen
88 source, especially in soils with low nitrification rates or immediately after fertilization when

89 concentrations can reach up to 40 mM (Britto and Kronzucker, 2002). Under these conditions,
90 NH_4^+ buildup can severely affect plant growth and development. For wheat, sole NH_4^+ nutrition
91 offers potential advantages, such as improved grain quality and increased tolerance to salinity
92 and cadmium stress (Ijato et al., 2020; Mousavi Shalmani et al., 2023). While wheat generally
93 favors NO_3^- , its preference can shift depending on environmental factors, making NH_4^+ more
94 beneficial in conditions like cold temperatures or rapid growth phases (Cramer et al., 1993;
95 Mousavi Shalmani et al., 2017). However, relying exclusively on NH_4^+ remains controversial due
96 to toxicity risks at high concentrations and wheat's overall inclination toward NO_3^- -based nutrition
97 (Bittsánszky et al., 2015).

98 Intraspecific variation in NH_4^+ uptake has been observed in species such as *Arabidopsis thaliana*
99 (Sarasketa et al., 2014), pea (*Pisum sativum*) (Cruz et al., 2011), rice (*Oryza sativa*) (Di et al., 2018),
100 and the grass model *Brachypodium distachyon* (De la Peña et al., 2024). These studies revealed
101 that certain accessions exhibit a preference for NH_4^+ as their primary nitrogen source, resulting in
102 improved biomass production and growth under sole NH_4^+ nutrition. The variation in ammonium
103 tolerance and capacity for NH_4^+ uptake offers a unique opportunity to develop strategies
104 combining stabilization of NH_4^+ -based fertilizers and plants able to take full advantage of such
105 fertilizers.

106 Ammonium also plays a crucial role in fungal physiology, influencing growth, metabolism, and
107 ecological interactions (Chutrakul et al., 2022). It serves as a key nitrogen source, regulating
108 fungal development through NH_4^+ transporters that facilitate nitrogen uptake. However, high NH_4^+
109 concentrations can exhibit fungistatic effects, inhibiting spore germination and fungal
110 proliferation, particularly in alkaline conditions (Liu et al., 2021). In a specific case study within
111 soil ecosystems, it was observed that NH_4^+ fertilization can alter fungal community composition,
112 often leading to an increase in the prevalence of pathogenic fungi such as *Blumeria* and
113 *Gaeumannomyces* (Maywald et al., 2022). Furthermore, "ammonia fungi", a unique group of fungi

114 that thrive in nitrogen-rich environments, exhibit remarkable adaptations to these conditions.
115 Around 70 species have been collected and identified following the application of urea or
116 ammonium-nitrogen, both in field and laboratory settings (Suzuki 2017). In symbiotic
117 relationships, like those in arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) from the *Glomeromycota* phylum,
118 these fungi assimilate NH_4^+ and facilitate its transfer by rapidly delivering it to the host plants
119 (Tanaka et al., 2005), underscoring its pivotal role in nutrient cycling. However, information
120 remains limited regarding the diversity of fungal communities under field conditions and their
121 response to NH_4^+ fertilization, particularly in terms of species composition, and functional roles,
122 that is crucial to develop stabilized NH_4^+ strategy.

123 This study aimed to assess the effectiveness and reliability of stabilized NH_4^+ fertilization strategy
124 (AS) in the field. Grain and straw yield were compared across different fertilization strategies,
125 including NH_4NO_3 (AN) and NO_3^- (NC) -based fertilizers, with different referent wheat varieties.
126 More, we also used stabilized NH_4^+ fertilization strategy in the field to identify varieties with good
127 yield performance under NH_4^+ fertilization among elite bread wheat varieties. Additionally, it
128 examined the environmental impact of stabilized NH_4^+ fertilization, particularly in terms of NO_3^-
129 losses, compared to other fertilization strategies. One specific year was dedicated to analyzing
130 the diversity and abundance of fungal communities in the soil and roots, focusing on the
131 differences between NH_4^+ and NO_3^- fertilization.

132 **2. Materials and methods**

133 **2.1 Field experiments**

134 The field studies to evaluate the impact of selected nitrogen fertilizers on four wheat varieties were
135 carried out during the 2021-2022 growing season (named “field 2022” experiment) at the
136 experimental Moulin field (50°34'16.6"N 4°46'00.6"E) of the Walloon Agricultural Research Centre
137 (Grand-Leez, Belgium), during the 2022-2023 growing season (named “field 2023” experiment) at
138 the experimental Zémont field (50°33'39.7"N 4°42'51.5"E) of the Walloon Agricultural Research

139 Centre (Gembloux, Belgium) and during the 2023-2024 growing season (named “field 2024”
140 experiment) at the experimental Ernage field (50°34'59.4"N 4°41'17.2"E) of the Walloon
141 Agricultural Research Centre (Ernage, Belgium). In all trials, the experimental design included four
142 main plots, each containing four 9.6 m long and 2 m wide subplots (4 varieties x 3 nitrogen
143 treatments). Within the subplots, four bread wheat varieties (*Triticum aestivum* L.) were sowed
144 (referred to as “referent varieties”): three grain wheat varieties – Cellule (Florimond-Desprez,
145 Cappelle-en-Pévèle, France), Boisseau (Saaten-Union Recherche, Estrées Saint Denis, France),
146 and KWS Smart (KWS GmbH, Einbeck, Germany) and one straw variety – Pajero (Lemaire-
147 Deffontaines, Auchy Lez Orchies, France). These varieties exhibit different biomass production in
148 hydroponic cultivation depending on the nitrogen source supplied. Cellule was characterized by
149 a preference for NH_4^+ and as named $(\text{NH}_4^+)_+$, while Boisseau, KWS Smart and Pajero exhibited a
150 preference for NH_4NO_3 and as named $(\text{NH}_4^+)_-$ (Blum et al., 2025). Three nitrogen treatments,
151 calcium nitrate at 15.5% nitrogen (Tropicote®, Yara International ASA, Oslo, Norway), or
152 ammonium nitrate at 27% nitrogen (N27, LitFert, Rennes, France) or ammonium sulfate at 21%
153 nitrogen with 0.8% DMPP (3,4-Dimethylpyrazole phosphate) to maximize NH_4^+ preservation
154 (NovaTec® Solub 21, Compo Expert, Levallois-Perret, France) were applied. Additionally,
155 supplemental DMPP (Vizura®, BASF, Ludwigshafen, Germany) was applied twice at a rate of 3
156 $\text{L}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ to prolong its effect. Only calcium nitrate or ammonium sulfate were used on the
157 experiment 2023-screening. For each fertilization treatment, two nitrogen application rates were
158 used during the season: either 120 units of nitrogen in 2023 and 2024 or 180 units in 2022 and
159 2024. These applications were split into three doses: 40-40-40 for the 120-unit treatment and 60-
160 60-60 for the 180-unit treatment for tillering during stem elongation, and flag leaf emergence
161 stages of wheat growth. The abbreviations used for the treatments are NC for nitrate, AN for
162 ammonium nitrate and AS for stabilized ammonium. All meteorological data (Figure S2) were
163 collected from the Sombrefe weather station (Agromet project, Agricultural Research Centre,
164 Gembloux, Belgium) .

165 An additional trial (named "2023-screening") was carried out in 2023 to evaluate the impact of
166 nitrogen fertilizers on a selection of elite varieties from the Belgian catalog (20 varieties: 4 varieties
167 referents + 16 elite varieties x 2 nitrogen treatments: stabilized ammonium and nitrate):
168 Chevignon (Saaten-Union Recherche, Estrées Saint Denis, France), Cubitus (Secobra Saatzucht
169 GmbH, Lemgo, Germany), Geluck (Secobra Maule, France), Hyking (Saaten-Union Recherche,
170 Estrées Saint Denis, France), KWS Extase (KWS GmbH, Einbeck, Germany), LG Apollo (Limagrain,
171 Saint-Beauzire, France), LG Character (Limagrain, Saint-Beauzire, France), LG Keramik
172 (Limagrain, Saint-Beauzire, France), LG Skyscraper (Limagrain, Saint-Beauzire, France), Positiv
173 (Florimond-Desprez, Cappelle-en-Pévèle, France), RGT Perkussio (RAGT Seeds, Rodez, France),
174 LG Spotlight (Limagrain, Saint-Beauzire, France), SY Admiration (Syngenta, Basel, Switzerland),
175 SY Insitor (Syngenta, Basel, Switzerland), SY Revolution (Syngenta, Basel, Switzerland) and,
176 Winner (Florimond-Desprez, Cappelle-en-Pévèle, France).

177 **2.2 Sampling and analysis of soil mineral content**

178 During the field study, soil samples were collected in March, April, May and June at a 0-30 cm soil
179 depth one to five days before and ten to fourteen days following each nitrogen application.
180 Comprehensive soil sampling plan for 2023 is shown in Figure 1. Additional soil samples at a 30-
181 60 cm and 60-90 cm depth were also collected in the "field 2024" experiment.

182 For each plot, eight soil samples were taken and pooled together. Mineral NO_3^- and NH_4^+ content
183 from the soil samples were analyzed: NO_3^- was measured using VCl_3 -Griess method
184 (Sulfanilamide/naphthylamine) as described by Miranda et al., (2001) and NH_4^+ by a method
185 based on the phenol hypochlorite assay (Berthelot reaction) described by Patton et al., (1977).
186 Measurement of P, K, Mg, Ca, C, N total, mineral N contents, pH and texture (Table S1) were
187 performed at a 0-30 cm soil depth before sowing (Provincial Laboratory, La Hulpe, Belgium).

188 **2.3 Sampling of soil and root for microbial analysis**

189 During the “field 2023” experiment, soil samples were collected in April, May and June 2023 at a
190 0-30 cm soil depth and the roots were collected in May and June 2023 from the whole plants
191 (Figure 1). The soil was then mixed and stored at -20°C. The roots were washed, and only thin
192 lateral roots were collected and stored at -20°C.

193 **2.4 Nitrous oxide emission measurement**

194 During the field 2024 trial, an LI-7820 gas analyzer (LI-COR, Lincoln, NE, USA) was used to
195 measure N₂O emissions from the soil following nitrogen application at the tillering stage on each
196 plot. Two closed chambers (500 × 325 mm²) were installed in subplots for the Cellule variety
197 (Figure S6), and emissions were monitored every two days during one week after nitrogen
198 application. N₂O concentrations (ppb) were recorded every second for two minutes. The “gas
199 fluxes package” for R was used to process the data, to estimate fluxes using Hutchinson-Mosier
200 regression (HMR) and robust linear regression, and to determine the best fit based on the
201 kappa.max threshold.

202 **2.5 Yield Components**

203 Harvests were conducted between August 6 and August 15 each year. To determine yield
204 components, measurements of grain yield, straw yield, and protein content were performed. For
205 grain yield, weights were recorded using a combine harvester equipped with an onboard weighing
206 system. A subsample of 1–2 kg was collected to determine moisture content, which was used to
207 normalize results. Grain yield was expressed in tons per hectare. For straw yield, straw was left to
208 dry in the field after harvest, then gathered using a fork and measured with a second pass of a
209 mini-combine harvester equipped with an onboard weighing system. Results were expressed in
210 tons per hectare. Additionally, grain moisture content and weight were measured using the GAC®
211 2100 BI (DICKEY-john, Auburn, IL, USA) for each plot sample, while grain protein content was
212 analyzed using the Infratec™ NOVA (FOSS, Hilleroed, Denmark). The four replicates of each

213 treatment were pooled for protein content analysis. Results were expressed in percentage of
214 protein of relative weight. ANOVA tests were considered as significant if $p < 0.05$.

215 **2.6 DNA extraction and quantitative PCR analysis**

216 Three samples from each subplot were collected from the soil and root batches and weighed. Soil
217 samples ranged from 0.25 to 0.35 g, while rinsed root samples weighed between 0.05 and 0.15 g.
218 DNA was extracted from the soil samples using the DNeasy PowerSoil® kit (Qiagen, Hilden,
219 Germany) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Prior to the root DNA extraction, roots were
220 crushed with mortar and pestle using liquid nitrogen and the fine powder was extracted with the
221 DNeasy Plant® kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). DNA concentration of each sample was measured
222 with the Quantus™ Fluorometer (Promega, Madison, WI, United States). For quantitative PCR only,
223 all DNA samples were then diluted to a concentration of $10 \text{ ng} \cdot \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ and stored at -20°C . Gene
224 abundances of each group of nitrifiers, denitrifiers, bacterial 16S rRNA, archaeal 16S rRNA,
225 Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi 18S rRNA and wheat TaTEF1 were quantified with Bio-Rad CFX96
226 Real Time System (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Hercules, CA, United States). The list of qPCR primers
227 and conditions are shown in Table S7. All qPCR programs ending with 5 s of 0.5°C increment from
228 65°C to 95°C for melt curve analysis. Working with a reaction volume of $10 \mu\text{L}$, $1 \mu\text{L}$ of sample DNA
229 was brought in a $9 \mu\text{L}$ mixture composed of $5 \mu\text{L}$ KAPA SYBR® FAST qPCR Master Mix (Kapa
230 Biosystems, Wilmington, MA, United States), $1 \mu\text{L}$ of each primer ($10 \mu\text{M}$) and $2 \mu\text{L}$ of nuclease-
231 free water and repeated in triplicate. Standard curves for each gene were created using ten-fold
232 serial dilutions of linearized plasmid DNA. The efficiencies of these curves ranged from 80% to
233 120%, with R^2 values between 0.90 and 0.98 for all target genes. The initial gene quantity per gram
234 of wet soil ($\text{nb} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) was calculated using the following formula:

235
$$\text{Initial gene quantity (nb.g}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{10^{(Ct-I) \div S} \times \text{DF}}{M}$$

236 Wherein Ct is the mean Ct-value of the three technical repetitions, I the intercept and S the slope
237 of the standard curve, DF the dilution factor of the sample DNA and M the wet mass of the soil
238 sample (g). Afterwards, nitrifiers and denitrifiers communities were quantified in proportion with
239 total bacterial or total archaeal content of the sample. In addition, relative qPCR was performed
240 to quantify AMF colonization in the root samples. The protocol used was based on Bodenhausen
241 et al. (2021): the 18S rRNA gene signal assigned as target was normalized to the wheat TaTEF1
242 gene (Translation elongation factor 1) assigned as reference. Signal ratios were determined using
243 the Normalized expression $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method on the Bio-Rad CFX Manager 3.1 software.

244 **2.7 High-throughput amplicon sequencing and bioinformatic analysis**

245 High-throughput sequencing of amplicons was used to characterize the soil and root-associated
246 fungal communities from the 2023 experiment. Briefly, a total of 30 ng of DNA template (measured
247 by Qubit Fluorometer) and ITS2 rRNA fusion primers (ITS3 and ITS4) (Table S7) were used for PCR.
248 The resulting PCR products were purified using Agencourt AMPure XP beads (Beckman Coulter
249 Life Sciences, Indianapolis, IN, United States) dissolved in elution buffer, and labeled to complete
250 library construction. The size and concentration of the libraries were analyzed with an Agilent
251 2100 Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, United States). Finally, the libraries were
252 sequenced on the DNB platform (MGI Tech, Shenzhen, China) based on their insert size by BGI
253 Tech Solutions (Hong-Kong). Raw data were filtered to generate high-quality clean reads by
254 removing low-quality, adapter-contaminated, ambiguous, or low-complexity sequences, and
255 assigning clean reads to samples based on barcode alignment using iTools Fqtools fqcheck v.0.25
256 (Droop et al., 2016), cutadapt v.2.6 (Martin et al., 2011) and readfq v1.0. Overlapping paired-end
257 reads were merged into a consensus sequence using FLASH v1.2.11 (Magoč et al., 2011). Tags
258 were clustered into OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) at a 97% similarity threshold using
259 UPARSE (Edgar et al., 2013), with chimeras filtered by UCHIME v4.2.40 (Edgar et al., 2011) and
260 reference databases, and tag mapping performed to generate an OTU abundance table using

261 USEARCH v7 .0.1090 (Edgar et al., 2010). OTU representative sequences were taxonomically
262 annotated using RDP Classifier v2.2 (Wang et al., 2024) and UNITE database (Abarenkov et al.,
263 2024) with a 0.6 identity threshold, and results were filtered to exclude unannotated OTUs or
264 taxonomies irrelevant to the research background (e.g. non-fungi) to generate the species
265 abundance table. Species abundance table was subsequently used for further investigations
266 including relative abundance at Phylum, Class, Order, Family, Genus and Species level and
267 species differential analysis. Ecological attributions were investigated through the MycoBank
268 (<https://www.mirri.org/>) and the Index Fungorum (<https://indexfungorum.org/>) databases.

269 **2.8 Statistical analysis**

270 Analysis was performed using R v3.4.1 (R Core Team, 2023). Alpha-diversity was monitored by
271 Chao index to report on the species richness of microbial community and Shannon index to report
272 on the species diversity of the community. Differential species screening using the Wilcoxon rank-
273 sum test was performed to identify differences between the two groups. ANOVA were considered
274 as significant if $p < 0.05$.

275 **3. Results**

276 **3.1 Yield performance of bread wheat varieties with stabilized ammonium fertilization**

277 The hypothesis is that the AS strategy could enhance NUE and, consequently, improve yield,
278 particularly when fertilization is either non-stabilized or in nitrate form. We tested different
279 varieties in field that had been previously characterized based on their performance on nitrogen
280 form. The grain and straw yield results from the three years are presented in Figure 2a and Figure
281 2b, respectively for each variety and fertilization strategies.

282 Overall, climate had a strong impact on yield, with grain yields ranging from 9 to 12 T ha⁻¹ in 2022
283 (hot and dry year) and 2023 (intermediate climate). However, in 2024, yields were significantly
284 lower, ranging from 2 to 6 T ha⁻¹ due to wet and cold weather conditions during the growing season

285 (Figure S2). Straw yields also varied, ranging from 4 to 6 T ha⁻¹ in 2022, 6 to 9 T ha⁻¹ in 2023, and 2
286 to 5 T ha⁻¹ in 2024. Over the three years of study, the genotype factor significantly influenced grain
287 yield (Table 1), and straw yield (Table 2).

288 In 2022, nitrogen inputs were set at 180 uN.ha⁻¹. The (NH₄⁺)⁺ variety fertilized with AS strategy
289 showed similar grain (Table 1) and straw (Table 2) yields to other fertilization strategies, except AN
290 for grain, which outperformed. In contrast, the (NH₄⁺)⁻ varieties exhibited varied responses:
291 Boisseau showed similar grain yields, but KWS Smart and Pajero achieved higher grain yields
292 under the NC strategy. Pajero and Boisseau produced similar straw yields across all strategies,
293 while KWS Smart had higher straw yields with the NC strategy.

294 In 2023, nitrogen inputs were reduced from 180 to 120 uN.ha⁻¹ to assess the impact of reduced
295 fertilization. The (NH₄⁺)⁺ variety with AS maintained grain and straw yields comparable to other
296 fertilization strategies. Additionally, the (NH₄⁺)⁻ varieties achieved similar grain and straw yields
297 across the different fertilization strategy.

298 In 2024, two nitrogen application rates were tested: 120 and 180 uN ha⁻¹. At 120 uN ha⁻¹, AS
299 resulted in both similar grain and straw yields for the (NH₄⁺)⁺ variety. Additionally, both grain and
300 straw yields were unchanged for the (NH₄⁺)⁻ varieties, but significantly lower yields for Boisseau
301 compared to AN and N. At 180 uN ha⁻¹, straw yields remained consistent across all fertilization
302 strategies for each variety. However, grain yields were lower for Boisseau under AN and for Pajero
303 under both AN and NC.

304 The protein content for each fertilization strategy is presented in Figure S3. For the AS strategy,
305 protein content ranged from 10.7% to 14.99%, while the AN strategy exhibited a range of 11.72%
306 to 15.3%. The NC strategy showed protein content ranging from 11.34% to 14.34%.

307 In the 2023-screening trial, we assessed the yield performance of elite varieties to identify
308 varieties with good yield performance under NH₄⁺ fertilization. Twenty varieties, including 16 elite
309 varieties, were tested with an application of 120 uN.ha⁻¹ (Figure 3). Among them, only SY

310 Admiration showed a significant increase in grain yield with AS compared to NC. Additionally,
311 under these conditions, SY Admiration (12.37 T.ha⁻¹), along with LG Skyscraper (12.40 T.ha⁻¹),
312 ranked among the highest-yielding varieties under the AS strategy. SY Insitor (12.52 T.ha⁻¹) and
313 Winner (12.34 T.ha⁻¹) under the NC strategy achieved the same yields (Table S2).

314 **3.2 Soil nitrogen content and dynamic in the stabilized ammonium strategy**

315 The hypothesis is that the AS fertilization strategy reduces nitrogen losses through leaching while
316 ensuring a better NH₄⁺ supply for wheat throughout the season. Figure 4 presents soil nitrogen
317 measurements during the 2022, 2023, and 2024 seasons for each fertilization strategy.
318 Specifically, cumulative NH₄⁺ levels are shown in Figure 4a, NO₃⁻ cumulative levels in Figure 4b,
319 and the NH₄⁺/NO₃⁻ ratio (ANR) in Figure 4c.

320 In 2022, a particularly warm year, the AS strategy with 180 uN.ha⁻¹ effectively maintained high NH₄⁺
321 levels, over 200 kg.N.ha⁻¹, and low NO₃⁻ levels, less than 20 kg.N.ha⁻¹, compared to other
322 fertilization methods. This stability was sustained throughout the growing season, with an ANR
323 between 90:10 and 95:5, ensuring continuous nutrient availability for the crop.

324 In 2023, which had intermediate climatic conditions, nitrogen inputs were reduced to 120 uN.ha⁻¹
325 ¹. As a result, cumulative NH₄⁺ levels for the AS strategy were around 50 kg.N.ha⁻¹ and remained
326 higher than those of the NC and AN strategies. The cumulative NO₃⁻ level for AS was lower,
327 between 30 and 40 kg.N.ha⁻¹, than for NC, and the NH₄⁺/NO₃⁻ ratio fluctuated throughout the
328 season, the ANR was between 50:50 and 90:10.

329 In 2024, two nitrogen application rates were tested: 120 and 180 uN.ha⁻¹. The season was cold
330 and wet. Cumulative NH₄⁺ levels in the AS strategy remained the highest, with higher values for
331 180 uN.ha⁻¹, between 50 and 100 kg.N.ha⁻¹, than for 120, around 50 kg.N.ha⁻¹. The cumulative NO₃⁻
332 levels were between 30 and 40 kg.N.ha⁻¹ but remained lower than in AN and NC. The NH₄⁺/NO₃⁻
333 ratio continued to fluctuate throughout the season under the AS strategy with an ANR between
334 20:80 and 80:20.

335 Additionally, in 2024, further analyses were conducted at different soil depths, specifically at 30–
336 60 cm and 60–90 cm (Figure S4b). Regardless of the fertilization strategy, nitrate levels were
337 significantly lower at these depths. The AS strategy effectively limits nitrate accumulation in the
338 0–30 cm horizon. However, at high nitrogen application rates (180 uN), nitrate levels are lower in
339 the 60–90 cm horizon.

340 In 2022, we also observed ANR in both bare soils and those with plant cover. Moreover, Figure S4a
341 highlights an interesting finding: regardless of the fertilization strategy, the presence of crops
342 helps sustain NH_4^+ levels in the soil.

343 During the intermediate year 2023, we also measured the abundance of soil microorganisms
344 involved in nitrification, including AOB and AOA, during April, May, and June (Figure S5 and Table
345 S4). The fertilization factor did not reveal significant differences in AOB abundance, although
346 median values were lower under the AS condition. While AOB abundance showed a decreasing
347 trend in the AS treatment, it remained relatively stable under NC fertilization; however, these
348 variations were not statistically significant according to the month factor. Similarly, no significant
349 differences in AOA abundance were observed between treatments during these months.

350 Figure S6 highlights the effectiveness of AS fertilization in reducing N_2O emissions in March 2024.
351 We measured N_2O emissions once soil temperatures exceeded 10°C . Spring is typically
352 associated with the beginning of N_2O emissions in many climatic regions (Lawrence et al., 2021).
353 In contrast, NC application leads to an emission peak the day after application, followed by a
354 gradual decline in the subsequent days. AN stands out with a consistently higher and more stable
355 N_2O flux throughout the measurement period. On average, over the 8-day analysis period,
356 emissions were reduced by approximately 75% with an application of $120 \text{ uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ and by 90% with
357 $180 \text{ uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ in our study. Differences of $6.5 \text{ g N}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ were observed between 120 and 180
358 $\text{uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ in AN or NC treatments, whereas this difference was only $1.7 \text{ g N}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ with AS (Table
359 S3).

360 **3.3 Diversity and abundance of soil and root-associated fungi during the intermediate year**

361 To our knowledge, no studies have specifically focused on fungal diversity and abundance in
362 relation to NH_4^+ fertilization. This study focused on the abundance and diversity of soil fungal
363 communities in April, May, and June 2023, as well as root-associated fungal communities in May
364 and June 2023, for the AS and NC fertilization strategies. These months correspond to different
365 stages of wheat growth: tillering in April, elongation in May, and flowering in June.

366 Alpha diversity indices, including the Chao1 index (species richness) and the Shannon index
367 (community diversity), did not show significant differences (Table 4) between treatments at the
368 tillering, elongation, and flowering stage for soil communities (Figure 5a). However, in root-
369 associated communities, no significant differences (Table 4) were observed at the elongation
370 stage, while the flowering stage showed significant differences for both indices (Figure 5c).

371 The number of observed operational taxonomic units (OTUs) was generally higher in soil (ranging
372 from 1,398 to 1,714) than in roots (ranging from 934 to 953). Most OTUs were shared between
373 treatments, with less than 20% being unique to each treatment (Figures 5b). In addition, root-
374 associated fungal communities under AS consistently exhibited a higher number of unique OTUs
375 (Figure 5d). Wilcoxon tests identified fungal taxa with significantly different abundances between
376 treatments in Figure S7, and their ecological attributions are provided in Table S5. In soil, 6 genera
377 differed significantly at the tillering stage, 27 at the elongation stage, and 40 at the flowering stage
378 (Figure S7a). In roots, 9 genera at the elongation stage and 29 at the flowering stage exhibited
379 significant differences (Figure S7b), with 25 of the latter being more abundant under AS
380 fertilization. Over time, fewer than 20 genera were consistently favored by AS in both soil and
381 roots. The most differentially abundant genera were saprophytic *Ascomycota* and *Basidiomycota*.
382 Certain genera such as *Alternaria* ($\log_2 = 1.67$, elongation stage, soil), *Phaeosphaeria* ($\log_2 = 1.20$,
383 elongation stage, soil), and *Thelonectria* ($\log_2 = 2.90$, flowering stage, soil) were more abundant
384 under AS fertilization and may be associated with plant diseases, including those affecting

385 cereals. However, no specific pathogens were identified at the species level. Conversely,
386 beneficial genera such as *Mortierella* ($\log_2 = 1.45$, elongation stage, soil; $\log_2 = 3.28$, flowering
387 stage, root) and *Vishniacozyma* ($\log_2 = 1.88$, elongation stage, soil; $\log_2 = 1.25$, flowering stage,
388 root) were also promoted by AS. In contrast, genera such as *Beauveria* ($\log_2 = -4.01$, elongation
389 stage, soil), *Falciphora* ($\log_2 = -1.79$, elongation stage, root), and *Trichoderma* ($\log_2 = -0.48$,
390 elongation stage, root), known for their plant-beneficial properties, were more abundant under
391 NC fertilization. Interestingly, *Fusarium* genus, capable of producing N_2O via NO_3^- or nitrite
392 reduction through denitrification or co-denitrification, were favored under NC fertilization in soil
393 ($\log_2 = -0.49$, flowering stage), representing 1.25% (AS) and 1.75% (NC) of relative abundance.
394 However, in root, *Fusarium* was slightly more abundant under AS ($\log_2 = 0.86$, flowering stage),
395 representing 0.49% (AS) and 0.27% (NC) of relative abundance.

396 The abundance of AMF, assessed via qPCR, was measured in root samples during the elongation
397 and the flowering stages (Figure 5e). While the treatment effect was not significant during the
398 elongation stage, it became significant during the flowering stage. These results indicate that AS
399 fertilization reduces root colonization by *Glomeromycota*. However, at the root level, Wilcoxon
400 test did not show significant differences between AS and NC at the genus level within the relative
401 abundance (Table S6). Among the 29 known *Glomeromycota* genera (Oehl et al., 2011), nine were
402 detected in the root samples, and four of the five orders of *Glomeromycota* including
403 *Archaeosporales*, *Glomerales*, *Diversisporales*, and *Gigasporales* in both treatments.

404 **4. Discussion**

405 **4.1 The stabilized ammonium fertilization has no or limited impact yield in climatic** 406 **conditions suitable for wheat cropping**

407 The objective of this study was to evaluate the impact of the AS strategy on yield parameters of
408 winter bread wheat within the northwestern European production context. In agricultural
409 contexts, the risk of NH_4^+ toxicity is elevated when NH_4^+ is the primary nitrogen source,

410 particularly directly after fertilization (Britto et al., 2002). To mitigate this issue, our approach
411 aimed to integrate wheat varieties previously assessed for their NH_4^+ uptake efficiency (Blum et
412 al., 2025). Although soil nitrogen measurements in our field experiment did not indicate complete
413 preservation of NH_4^+ in the soil, a higher NH_4^+ content was observed with AS fertilization
414 compared to AN fertilization.

415 Field study results indicate that the effectiveness of the AS strategy is highly influenced by climatic
416 conditions. During the intermediate climate year, this approach maintained grain and straw yields
417 at levels comparable to other fertilization strategies, regardless of the variety. Under warm and dry
418 conditions, both grain and straw yields remained stable, but except for Boisseau, (NH_4^+)- varieties
419 showed better grain yields with NC. However, in cold and humid conditions, straw yields were
420 preserved, while grain yields varied depending on the fertilization strategy. Moreover, in the same
421 year, we compared two fertilizer application rates: 120 and 180 $\text{uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$. The grain yields of Cellule,
422 KWS Smart, and Pajero, as well as the straw yields of all varieties, were similar at 120 $\text{uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$. This
423 finding suggests that 120 $\text{uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ is sufficient to maintain yields under the AS strategy, highlighting
424 the potential to reduce nitrogen inputs without compromising productivity.

425 Over the three years of evaluation, the yield results from the AS fertilization strategy were, at best,
426 comparable to those obtained with other fertilization approaches, showing no significant yield
427 improvement with the referent varieties. Particularly, the variety (NH_4^+)+ consistently met this
428 criterion, maintaining relatively stable yields across different fertilization methods. In contrast,
429 the (NH_4^+)- varieties demonstrated favorable responses only under specific conditions, such as
430 in 2024 at 120 $\text{uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$, for both grain and straw production. Furthermore, our results indicate that
431 the preservation of yields through the AS strategy is largely driven by genetic factors. Our
432 evaluation of 16 elite varieties in 2023 showed varying grain yields between AS and NC fertilization
433 strategies. Interestingly, one elite variety outperformed the reference varieties under AS
434 fertilization, achieving superior yields and reaching the highest grain yield. This suggests that

435 genetic control may play a crucial role in enhancing adaptation to AS fertilization. Studies on the
436 genotype diversity of plants for their ability to preferentially develop on NH_4^+ remain limited, and
437 have mainly focused on a few species, including rice (Di et al., 2018), and the grass model
438 *Brachypodium distachyon* (De la Peña et al., 2024) for monocots. The ability to assimilate
439 NH_4^+ may be correlated to the plant's capacity to overcome NH_4^+ toxicity. Several mechanisms
440 have been identified to help plants manage NH_4^+ toxicity, including regulating of NH_4^+ uptake
441 (Straub et al., 2017), detoxifying reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Xie et al., 2015), maintaining ionic
442 balance by increasing potassium levels (Szczerba et al., 2008), and activating signaling pathways
443 of plant hormones like abscisic acid (Li et al. 2012), auxin (Di et al., 2021), and brassinosteroids
444 (Devi et al., 2022). Wheat breeding relies on yield as a crucial trait, and improving this trait requires
445 efficient NUE that encompasses nitrogen uptake and utilization use. A large number of
446 quantitative trait loci (QTLs) (Brasier et al., 2020) and candidate genes (Islam et al., 2021) in wheat
447 for improving NUE have been reported and could be useful for the development of molecular
448 markers and the improvement of NUE under AS fertilization.

449 **4.2 Stabilized Ammonium Fertilization: Enhancing Ammonium Availability for Wheat While** 450 **Reducing Nitrate Leaching**

451 Our results indicate that the AS strategy efficiently maintained NO_3^- levels at lower rates
452 compared to other fertilization strategies. Furthermore, our findings showed that these low NO_3^-
453 levels were unaffected by the year and consequently climate conditions. The cumulative NO_3^-
454 concentration remained regulated during the hot and dry year, even with nitrogen inputs of 180
455 $\text{uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$, which also coincided with the highest cumulative NH_4^+ levels. Consequently, AS strategy
456 makes higher availability of NH_4^+ to plants than the other fertilization strategies. During the cold
457 and humid year, there was no observed increase in NO_3^- conversion for AS strategy between the
458 two application rates (120 and 180 $\text{uN}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$). Because of NO_3^- levels remained constant in deeper
459 soil layers, the efficiency of the AS strategy was found in the upper soil horizon.

460 During the warm season, a stable $\text{NH}_4^+/\text{NO}_3^-$ ratio and consistently high NH_4^+ levels throughout
461 the season appeared to favor the AS strategy. In the other two years, with more samplings, the
462 $\text{NH}_4^+/\text{NO}_3^-$ ratio was only partially maintained and could be explained by a limitation of
463 nitrification inhibitor activity over time.

464 To further investigate the impact of AS, we analyzed the abundance of AOB and AOA during the
465 intermediate year. Despite the presence of NH_4^+ , the primary substrate for nitrification, AOB
466 populations did not increase over time and remained at levels comparable to NC. This suggests
467 that the nitrification inhibitor included in the AS strategy effectively contained AOB abundance.

468 We also observed N_2O emissions during one week in spring of the wet year when the soil
469 temperatures reached 10°C and N_2O emission are supposed to start. The trend observed in NO_3^- -
470 based fertilization can be attributed to the nitrification of its non-stabilized NH_4^+ content. The
471 expected effects of AS fertilization are observed: the peak of nitrogen production is contained
472 within the first few days, and levels remain lower compared to other fertilization types. This early
473 peak has also been reported in other microcosm studies, occurring three days after fertilizer
474 application (Li et al., 2023).

475 **4.3 The AS fertilization strategy does not significantly affect soil fungal communities, but** 476 **changes root-associated fungal diversity and abundance at flowering time**

477 Soil and rhizospheric fungi play a crucial role in agriculture, enhancing plant fitness and
478 performance. They are generally classified into three major functional groups based on their
479 ecological roles and lifestyles: symbiotic, pathogenic, and saprophytic fungi. However, the
480 abundance and composition of fungal communities are influenced by agricultural practices,
481 including fertilizer application (Jannoura et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2021).

482 The impact NH_4^+ and NO_3^- fertilization strategy on fungal communities remains largely
483 unexplored. In pot experiments on wheat, Maywald et al., (2022) observed modifications in fungal
484 community composition and structure between NH_4^+ and NO_3^- fertilization with a higher richness

485 of taxa but a higher abundance of fungal pathogenic taxa in the NH_4^+ -fertilized treatment. Our
486 results were collected in field conditions during an intermediate climate year across 3 critical
487 developmental stages of wheat. The absence of significant results on alpha diversity for the
488 majority of the samplings indicates that the AS fertilization strategies did not induce drastic
489 changes.

490 Alpha diversity indicators showed that only fertilization with AS can lead to significantly enhanced
491 higher richness and diversity in root-associated fungal communities during the wheat flowering
492 time. At the flowering stage, a lower number of observed OTUs in the NC strategy could explain
493 the significant differences in diversity. The flowering stage of plants is believed to apply a stronger
494 selective pressure on the rhizosphere microbiome compared to the vegetative phase (Walters et
495 al., 2018; Dilla-Ermita et al., 2021). It is generally associated with the maximum secretion of
496 exudates, a peak in the quantity of organic carbon, and various aromatic compounds, such as
497 amino acids and carboxylic acids, which can be linked to the structure of the rhizosphere
498 microbiota (Zhalnina et al., 2018). Thus, at flowering time, NH_4^+ nutrition could have reorganized
499 exudate composition and subsequently shaped the root microbiome.

500 On the other hand, the flowering stage was the period with the greatest number of taxonomic
501 differences between the two fertilizations: 40 genera in soil and 29 in roots. The study also
502 highlighted genera with functional impacts on plants, both beneficial and pathogenic. AS
503 fertilization favored several potential pathogens affecting cereals, while different beneficial
504 genera were favored by each fertilization type. During the flowering stage, AS fertilization reduced
505 the abundance of *Glomeromycota* communities in wheat roots compared to NC fertilization.
506 These findings align with studies indicating that NO_3^- favors *Glomeromycota* colonization over
507 NH_4^+ in some plant species, potentially due to NH_4^+ toxicity (Lambert and Weidensaul, 1991;
508 Boukcim et al., 2001; Hawkins and George, 2001). However, laboratory studies suggest that NH_4^+
509 facilitates a faster nitrogen transfer to plants via AMF compared to NO_3^- (Tanaka et al., 2005).

510 5. Conclusion

511 Wheat accounts for 18% of global fertilizer use, but with a nitrogen use efficiency of only 48%, a
512 significant portion of applied nitrogen is lost and contributes to environment issues. Stabilized
513 NH_4^+ fertilization (AS) is an effective strategy to reduce NO_3^- losses, and the design of variety-
514 specific for this fertilization can further enhance its benefits. Integrating these two approaches
515 has the potential to improve both crop productivity and environmental sustainability. Our study
516 focused on evaluating the yield performance of stabilized AS fertilization in combination with
517 wheat varieties previously identified in laboratory conditions for NH_4^+ uptake. Over three years of
518 field experiments, we observed that achieving yields comparable to those of conventional
519 fertilization strategies depended on the genotype: (i) comparable yields were obtained for the
520 variety exhibiting a preference for NH_4^+ , and (ii) yields were comparable but climate-dependent
521 for varieties exhibiting a preference for NH_4NO_3 . Furthermore, we identified one elite wheat variety
522 capable of achieving higher yields under AS fertilization, suggesting a genetic control of grain yield
523 trait under AS strategy. From an environmental perspective, AS fertilization effectively reduced
524 soil NO_3^- levels by slowing nitrification and limiting N_2O emissions over the study period. During
525 the intermediate year, while overall fungal alpha diversity and richness in soil and roots remained
526 unchanged between AS and NC fertilization, notable shifts occurred during the flowering stage—
527 a key period of microbial dynamics in the rhizosphere. Specifically, AS fertilization increased
528 fungal alpha diversity richness but led to a reduction in AMF abundance. Overall, this study
529 employed an integrative approach to assess both the agronomic performance and environmental
530 impact of AS fertilization on bread wheat over a large period trials. By combining these
531 perspectives, our findings strengthen the credibility of this strategy and highlight its potential for
532 integration into wheat production systems, paving the way for more sustainable nitrogen
533 management.

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539 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

540 AB, HV, FH, and CT conceived the original idea. AB wrote the manuscript. AB, ML and YM carried
541 out the experiments. AB and ML carried out data processing. FH and HV fundings.

542 **Declaration of competing interest**

543 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest or personal relationships that could be
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549 **Data availability**

550 The datasets of the fungal ITS2 metabarcoding supporting the conclusions of this article are
551 available in the SRA database under the reference PRJNA1237279.

552

553 **References**

- 554 1. Abarenkov, K., Nilsson, R. H., Larsson, K. H., Taylor, A. F., May, T. W., Frøslev, T. G., ... &
555 Kõljalg, U. (2024). The UNITE database for molecular identification and taxonomic
556 communication of fungi and other eukaryotes: sequences, taxa and classifications
557 reconsidered. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 52(D1), D791-D797.
- 558 2. Aldossari, N., & Ishii, S. (2021). Fungal denitrification revisited—Recent advancements and
559 future opportunities. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 157, 108250.
- 560 3. Arregui, L. M., & Quemada, M. (2008). Strategies to improve nitrogen use efficiency in
561 winter cereal crops under rainfed conditions. *Agronomy Journal*, 100(2), 277-284.
- 562 4. Beeckman, F., Annetta, L., Corrochano-Monsalve, M., Beeckman, T., & Motte, H. (2024).
563 Enhancing agroecosystem nitrogen management: microbial insights for improved
564 nitrification inhibition. *Trends in Microbiology*, 32(6), 590-601.
- 565 5. Bittsánszky, A., Pilinszky, K., Gyulai, G., & Komives, T. (2015). Overcoming ammonium
566 toxicity. *Plant Science*, 231, 184-190
- 567 6. Blum, A., Jáuregui, I., Muhovski, Y., & Vanderschuren, H. (2025). Transcriptomic Profiling
568 Identifies Determinant Regulation for Ammonium Tolerance in Wheat. Zenodo.
569 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15105178>
- 570 7. Boukcim, H., Pages, L., Plassard, C., & Mousain, D. (2001). Root system architecture and
571 receptivity to mycorrhizal infection in seedlings of *Cedrus atlantica* as affected by nitrogen
572 source and concentration. *Tree Physiology*, 21(2-3), 109-115.
- 573 8. Bozal-Leorri, A., Subbarao, G. V., Kishii, M., Urmeneta, L., Kommerell, V., Karwat, H., ... &
574 González-Moro, M. B. (2022). Biological nitrification inhibitor-trait enhances nitrogen
575 uptake by suppressing nitrifier activity and improves ammonium assimilation in two elite
576 wheat varieties. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13, 1034219.
- 577 9. Brasier, K., Ward, B., Smith, J., Seago, J., Oakes, J., Balota, M., ... & Griffey, C. (2020).
578 Identification of quantitative trait loci associated with nitrogen use efficiency in winter
579 wheat. *PLoS One*, 15(2), e0228775.
- 580 10. Britto, D. T., & Kronzucker, H. J. (2002). NH_4^+ toxicity in higher plants: a critical review.
581 *Journal of plant physiology*, 159(6), 567-584.
- 582 11. Cassman, K. G., Dobermann, A., & Walters, D. T. (2002). Agroecosystems, nitrogen-use
583 efficiency, and nitrogen management. *AMBIO: A Journal of the Human Environment*, 31(2),
584 132-140.
- 585 12. Chen, A., Lei, B., Hu, W., Lu, Y., Mao, Y., Duan, Z., & Shi, Z. (2015). Characteristics of
586 ammonia volatilization on rice grown under different nitrogen application rates and its
587 quantitative predictions in Erhai Lake Watershed, China. *Nutrient Cycling in*
588 *Agroecosystems*, 101, 139-152.
- 589 13. Chutrakul, C., Panchanawaporn, S., Vorapreeda, T., Jeennor, S., Anantayanon, J., &
590 Laoteng, K. (2022). The exploring functional role of ammonium transporters of *Aspergillus*
591 *oryzae* in nitrogen metabolism: challenges towards cell biomass production.
592 *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(14), 7567.
- 593 14. Coskun, D., Britto, D. T., Shi, W., & Kronzucker, H. J. (2017). Nitrogen transformations in
594 modern agriculture and the role of biological nitrification inhibition. *Nature plants*, 3(6), 1-
595 10.
- 596 15. Cramer, M. D., & Lewis, O. A. M. (1993). The influence of nitrate and ammonium nutrition
597 on the growth of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and maize (*Zea mays*) plants. *Annals of Botany*,
598 72(4), 359-365.
- 599 16. Cruz, C., Domínguez-Valdivia, M. D., Aparicio-Tejo, P. M., Lamsfus, C., Bio, A., Martins-
600 Loução, M. A., & Moran, J. F. (2011). Intra-specific variation in pea responses to
601 ammonium nutrition leads to different degrees of tolerance. *Environmental and*
602 *Experimental Botany*, 70(2-3), 233-243.

- 603 17. Daims, H., Lückner, S., & Wagner, M. (2016). A new perspective on microbes formerly
604 known as nitrite-oxidizing bacteria. *Trends in microbiology*, 24(9), 699-712.
- 605 18. De la Peña, M., Poucet, T., Montardit-Tarda, F., Urmeneta, L., Urbano-Gámez, J. A.,
606 Cassan, C.,... & Marino, D. (2024). Natural variation in the adjustment of primary
607 metabolism determines ammonium tolerance in the model grass *Brachypodium*
608 *distachyon*. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 75(22), 7237-7253.
- 609 19. Devi, L. L., Pandey, A., Gupta, S., & Singh, A. P. (2022). The interplay of auxin and
610 brassinosteroid signaling tunes root growth under low and different nitrogen forms. *Plant*
611 *physiology*, 189(3), 1757-1773.
- 612 20. Di, D. W., Sun, L., Wang, M., Wu, J., Kronzucker, H. J., Fang, S.,... & Li, G. (2021). WRKY46
613 promotes ammonium tolerance in *Arabidopsis* by repressing NUDX9 and indole-3-acetic
614 acid-conjugating genes and by inhibiting ammonium efflux in the root elongation zone.
615 *New Phytologist*, 232(1), 190-207.
- 616 21. Di, D. W., Sun, L., Zhang, X., Li, G., Kronzucker, H. J., & Shi, W. (2018). Involvement of auxin
617 in the regulation of ammonium tolerance in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Plant and Soil*, 432, 373-
618 387.
- 619 22. Dilla-Ermita, C. J., Lewis, R. W., Sullivan, T. S., & Hulbert, S. H. (2021). Wheat genotype-
620 specific recruitment of rhizosphere bacterial microbiota under controlled environments.
621 *Frontiers in plant science*, 12, 718264.
- 622 23. Droop, A. P. (2016). fqtools: an efficient software suite for modern FASTQ file
623 manipulation. *Bioinformatics*, 32(12), 1883-1884
- 624 24. Edgar, R. C. (2010). Search and clustering orders of magnitude faster than BLAST.
625 *Bioinformatics*, 26(19), 2460-2461.
- 626 25. Edgar, R. C. (2013). UPARSE: highly accurate OTU sequences from microbial amplicon
627 reads. *Nature methods*, 10(10), 996-998.
- 628 26. Edgar, R. C., Haas, B. J., Clemente, J. C., Quince, C., & Knight, R. (2011). UCHIME improves
629 sensitivity and speed of chimera detection. *Bioinformatics*, 27(16), 2194-2200.
- 630 27. Erisman, J. W., Galloway, J., Seitzinger, S., Bleeker, A., & Butterbach-Bahl, K. (2011).
631 Reactive nitrogen in the environment and its effect on climate change. *Current Opinion in*
632 *Environmental Sustainability*, 3(5), 281-290.
- 633 28. FAO, 2024. Highlights, Inorganic fertilizers. 2002–2022.
634 [https://www.fao.org/statistics/highlights-archive/highlights-detail/inorganic-fertilizers-](https://www.fao.org/statistics/highlights-archive/highlights-detail/inorganic-fertilizers-2002-2022/en)
635 [2002-2022/en](https://www.fao.org/statistics/highlights-archive/highlights-detail/inorganic-fertilizers-2002-2022/en)
- 636 29. Galloway, J. N., Townsend, A. R., Erisman, J. W., Bekunda, M., Cai, Z., Freney, J. R., ... &
637 Sutton, M. A. (2008). Transformation of the nitrogen cycle: recent trends, questions, and
638 potential solutions. *Science*, 320(5878), 889-892.
- 639 30. Hawkins, H. J., & George, E. (2001). Reduced¹⁵N-nitrogen transport through arbuscular
640 mycorrhizal hyphae to *Triticum aestivum* L. supplied with ammonium vs. nitrate nutrition.
641 *Annals of Botany*, 87(3), 303-311.
- 642 31. Hayatsu, M., Tago, K., & Saito, M. (2008). Various players in the nitrogen cycle: diversity
643 and functions of the microorganisms involved in nitrification and denitrification. *Soil*
644 *Science and Plant Nutrition*, 54(1), 33-45.
- 645 32. Helgason, T., Daniell, T. J., Husband, R., Fitter, A. H., & Young, J. P. W. (1998). Ploughing up
646 the wood-wide web?. *Nature*, 394(6692), 431-431.
- 647 33. Hewins, C. R., Carrino-Kyker, S. R., & Burke, D. J. (2015). Seasonal variation in mycorrhizal
648 fungi colonizing roots of *Allium tricoccum* (wild leek) in a mature mixed hardwood forest.
649 *Mycorrhiza*, 25(6), 469-483.
- 650 34. Ijato, T., Porrás-Murillo, R., Ganz, P., Ludewig, U., & Neuhäuser, B. (2021). Concentration-
651 dependent physiological and transcriptional adaptations of wheat seedlings to
652 ammonium. *Physiologia Plantarum*, 171(3), 328-342.
- 653 35. Islam, S., Zhang, J., Zhao, Y., She, M., & Ma, W. (2021). Genetic regulation of the traits
654 contributing to wheat nitrogen use efficiency. *Plant Science*, 303, 110759.

- 655 36. Jannoura, R., Joergensen, R. G., & Bruns, C. (2014). Organic fertilizer effects on growth,
656 crop yield, and soil microbial biomass indices in sole and intercropped peas and oats
657 under organic farming conditions. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 52, 259-270.
- 658 37. Klindworth, A., Pruesse, E., Schweer, T., Peplies, J., Quast, C., Horn, M., & Glöckner, F. O.
659 (2013). Evaluation of general 16S ribosomal RNA gene PCR primers for classical and next-
660 generation sequencing-based diversity studies. *Nucleic acids research*, 41(1), e1-e1
- 661 38. Kowalchuk, G. A., & Stephen, J. R. (2001). Ammonia-oxidizing bacteria: a model for
662 molecular microbial ecology. *Annual Reviews in Microbiology*, 55(1), 485-529.
- 663 39. Ladha, J. K., Pathak, H., Krupnik, T. J., Six, J., & van Kessel, C. (2005). Efficiency of fertilizer
664 nitrogen in cereal production: retrospects and prospects. *Advances in agronomy*, 87, 85-
665 156.
- 666 40. Ladha, J. K., Tirol-Padre, A., Reddy, C. K., Cassman, K. G., Verma, S., Powlson, D. S., ... &
667 Pathak, H. (2016). Global nitrogen budgets in cereals: A 50-year assessment for maize,
668 rice and wheat production systems. *Scientific reports*, 6(1), 1-9.
- 669 41. Lambert, D. H., & Weidensaul, T. C. (1991). Element uptake by mycorrhizal soybean from
670 sewage-sludge-treated soil. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 55(2), 393-398.
- 671 42. Lawrence, N. C., Tenesaca, C. G., VanLoocke, A., & Hall, S. J. (2021). Nitrous oxide
672 emissions from agricultural soils challenge climate sustainability in the US Corn Belt.
673 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(46), e2112108118.
- 674 43. Leininger, S., Urlich, T., Schloter, M., Schwark, L., Qi, J., Nicol, G. W., ... & Schleper, C.
675 (2006). Archaea predominate among ammonia-oxidizing prokaryotes in soils. *Nature*,
676 442(7104), 806-809.
- 677 44. Li, B., Li, Q., Xiong, L., Kronzucker, H. J., Krämer, U., & Shi, W. (2012). Arabidopsis plastid
678 AMOS1/EGY1 integrates abscisic acid signaling to regulate global gene expression
679 response to ammonium stress. *Plant Physiology*, 160(4), 2040-2051.
- 680 45. Li, H. R., Song, X. T., Bakken, L. R., & Ju, X. T. (2023). Reduction of N₂O emissions by DMPP
681 depends on the interactions of nitrogen sources (digestate vs. urea) with soil properties.
682 *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*. 22(1). 251-264.
- 683 46. Liu, T., Long, X., Zhou, J. P., Tian, D. W., Yang, Y. H., Zou, C. G., ... & Zhang, K. Q. (2021).
684 Fungistatic mechanism of ammonia against nematode-trapping fungus *Arthrobotrys*
685 *oligospora*, and strategy for this fungus to survive ammonia. *Msystems*, 6(5), 10-1128.
- 686 47. Magoč, T., & Salzberg, S. L. (2011). FLASH: fast length adjustment of short reads to
687 improve genome assemblies. *Bioinformatics*, 27(21), 2957-2963.
- 688 48. Martin, M. (2011). Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput
689 sequencing reads. *EMBnet journal*, 17(1), 10-12.
- 690 49. Maywald, N. J., Mang, M., Pahls, N., Neumann, G., Ludewig, U., & Francioli, D. (2022).
691 Ammonium fertilization increases the susceptibility to fungal leaf and root pathogens in
692 winter wheat. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13, 946584.
- 693 50. Miranda, K. M., Espey, M. G., & Wink, D. A. (2001). A rapid, simple spectrophotometric
694 method for simultaneous detection of nitrate and nitrite. *Nitric oxide*. 5(1). 62-71.
- 695 51. Mousavi Shalmani, M. A., Lakzian, A., Khorassani, R., Khavazi, K., & Zaman, M. (2017).
696 Interaction of different wheat genotypes and nitrification inhibitor 3, 4-dimethylpyrazole
697 phosphate using ¹⁵N isotope tracing techniques. *Communications in Soil Science and*
698 *Plant Analysis*, 48(11), 1247-1258.
- 699 52. Mousavi Shalmani, M. A., Lakzian, A., Khorassani, R., Zaman, M., Feiziasl, V., Borzouei,
700 A.,... & Naserian Khiabani, B. (2023). Nitrification inhibitor application at stem elongation
701 stage increases soil nitrogen availability and wheat nitrogen use efficiency under drought
702 stress. *Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science*, 69(11), 2020-2037.
- 703 53. Nicol, G. W., Leininger, S., Schleper, C., & Prosser, J. I. (2008). The influence of soil pH on
704 the diversity, abundance and transcriptional activity of ammonia oxidizing archaea and
705 bacteria. *Environmental microbiology*, 10(11), 2966-2978.8

- 706 54. Ochsenreiter, T., Selezi, D., Quaiser, A., Bonch-Osmolovskaya, L., & Schleper, C. (2003).
707 Diversity and abundance of Crenarchaeota in terrestrial habitats studied by 16S RNA
708 surveys and real time PCR. *Environmental Microbiology*, 5(9), 787-797.
- 709 55. Oehl, F., Silva, G. A. D., Goto, B. T., & Sieverding, E. (2011). Glomeromycota: three new
710 genera and glomoid species reorganized. *Mycotaxon*, 116(1), 75-120.
- 711 56. Patton, C. J., & Crouch, S. R. (1977). Spectrophotometric and kinetics investigation of the
712 Berthelot reaction for the determination of ammonia. *Analytical chemistry*, 49(3), 464-
713 469.
- 714 57. Rotthauwe, J. H., Witzel, K. P., & Liesack, W. (1997). The ammonia monooxygenase
715 structural gene *amoA* as a functional marker: molecular fine-scale analysis of natural
716 ammonia-oxidizing populations. *Applied and environmental microbiology*, 63(12), 4704-
717 4712.
- 718 58. Sarasketa, A., González-Moro, M. B., González-Murua, C., & Marino, D. (2014). Exploring
719 ammonium tolerance in a large panel of *Arabidopsis thaliana* natural accessions. *Journal*
720 *of experimental botany*, 65(20), 6023-6033.
- 721 59. Statista Search Department, 2024. Consumption of nitrogenous fertilizers worldwide in
722 2022, by product. [https://www.statista.com/statistics/1288255/global-consumption-of-](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1288255/global-consumption-of-nitrogen-fertilizer-by-product/)
723 [nitrogen-fertilizer-by-product/](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1288255/global-consumption-of-nitrogen-fertilizer-by-product/)
- 724 60. Straub, T., Ludewig, U., & Neuhäuser, B. (2017). The kinase CIPK23 inhibits ammonium
725 transport in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *The Plant Cell*, 29(2), 409-422.
- 726 61. Subbarao, G. V., & Searchinger, T. D. (2021). A “more ammonium solution” to mitigate
727 nitrogen pollution and boost crop yields. *Proceedings of the National Academy of*
728 *Sciences*, 118(22), e2107576118.
- 729 62. Subbarao, G. V., Yoshihashi, T., Worthington, M., Nakahara, K., Ando, Y., Sahrawat, K. L.,
730 ... & Braun, H. J. (2015). Suppression of soil nitrification by plants. *Plant science*, 233, 155-
731 164.
- 732 63. Suzuki, A. (2017). Various aspects of ammonia fungi. *Developments in fungal biology and*
733 *applied mycology*, 39-58.
- 734 64. Szczerba, M. W., Britto, D. T., Balkos, K. D., & Kronzucker, H. J. (2008). Alleviation of rapid,
735 futile ammonium cycling at the plasma membrane by potassium reveals K⁺-sensitive
736 and-insensitive components of NH₄⁺ transport. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 59(2),
737 303-313.
- 738 65. Tanaka, Y., & Yano, K. (2005). Nitrogen delivery to maize via mycorrhizal hyphae depends
739 on the form of N supplied. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 28(10), 1247-1254.
- 740 66. Tufail, M. A., Ayyub, M., Tariq, L., Iltaf, J., Asbat, A., Bashir, I., & Umar, W. (2024). Nitrogen
741 fertilizers and the future of sustainable agriculture: a deep dive into production, pollution,
742 and mitigation measures. *Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 1-21.
- 743 67. Walker, A. W., Martin, J. C., Scott, P., Parkhill, J., Flint, H. J., & Scott, K. P. (2015). 16S rRNA
744 gene-based profiling of the human infant gut microbiota is strongly influenced by sample
745 processing and PCR primer choice. *Microbiome*, 3, 1-11.
- 746 68. Walters, W. A., Jin, Z., Youngblut, N., Wallace, J. G., Sutter, J., Zhang, W., ... & Ley, R. E.
747 (2018). Large-scale replicated field study of maize rhizosphere identifies heritable
748 microbes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(28), 7368-7373.
- 749 69. Wang, Q., & Cole, J. R. (2024). Updated RDP taxonomy and RDP Classifier for more
750 accurate taxonomic classification. *Microbiology Resource Announcements*, 13(4),
751 e01063-23.
- 752 70. Wei, Y., Xiong, S., Zhang, Z., Meng, X., Wang, L., Zhang, X., ... & Ma, X. (2021). Localization,
753 gene expression, and functions of glutamine synthetase isozymes in wheat grain (*Triticum*
754 *aestivum* L.). *Frontiers in plant science*, 12, 580405.
- 755 71. Weiske, A., Benckiser, G., Herbert, T., & Ottow, J. (2001). Influence of the nitrification
756 inhibitor 3, 4-dimethylpyrazole phosphate (DMPP) in comparison to dicyandiamide (DCD)

757 on nitrous oxide emissions, carbon dioxide fluxes and methane oxidation during 3 years
758 of repeated application in field experiments. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 34, 109-117.
759 72. White, T. J., Bruns, T., Lee, S. J. W. T., & Taylor, J. (1990). Amplification and direct sequencing
760 of fungal ribosomal RNA genes for phylogenetics. *PCR protocols: a guide to methods and*
761 *applications*, 18(1), 315-322.
762 73. Wu, L., Li, Z., Zhao, F., Zhao, B., Phillip, F. O., Feng, J., ... & Yu, K. (2021). Increased organic
763 fertilizer and reduced chemical fertilizer increased fungal diversity and the abundance of
764 beneficial fungi on the grape berry surface in arid areas. *Frontiers in microbiology*, 12,
765 628503.
766 74. Xie, Y., Mao, Y., Xu, S., Zhou, H., Duan, X., Cui, W.,... & Xu, G. (2015). Heme-heme
767 oxygenase 1 system is involved in ammonium tolerance by regulating antioxidant defence
768 in *Oryza sativa*. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 38(1), 129-143.
769 75. Zhalnina, K., Louie, K. B., Hao, Z., Mansoori, N., Da Rocha, U. N., Shi, S., ... & Brodie, E. L.
770 (2018). Dynamic root exudate chemistry and microbial substrate preferences drive
771 patterns in rhizosphere microbial community assembly. *Nature microbiology*, 3(4), 470-
772 480.
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a)

777 **Figure 1:** Overview of the experimentation in 2023. a) Sampling and cultivation plan, including
778 fertilizer applications, soil sampling for various analyses, and harvest. b) Photographs of the
779 experimental trial in May 2023.

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782 **Figure 2:** Yield components measurements under different fertilization strategies over the 3 years
783 trial for the referent varieties: Cellule, Boisseau, KWS Smart, and Pajero. a) Grain yields ($T ha^{-1}$),
784 and b) straws yields ($T ha^{-1}$). Mean, standard deviation and ANOVA results are shown in Table 1
785 for grain, and Table 2 for straw. AS = Ammonium (blue) ; AN = Ammonium Nitrate (green) ; NC =
786 Nitrate (orange).

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2023 - screening
Grain yield (T ha⁻¹)

789 **Figure 3:** Grain yields ($T\ ha^{-1}$) for the elite wheat varieties. Asterisk indicates variety with
790 significant changes between AS and NC grain yields. Mean, standard deviation and ANOVA results
791 are shown in Table S2. AS = Ammonium (blue) ; NC = Nitrate (orange).

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794 **Figure 4:** Soil nitrogen content under different fertilization strategies over the 3 years trial.
795 Cumulative content (kg N ha⁻¹) of soil a) ammonium and b) nitrate. c) Proportion (%) of soil
796 ammonium (blue) and nitrate (orange) content throughout the season. T1 corresponds to the date
797 before the first fertilizer application, while T2 to T7 are after the applications.
798

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a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

800 **Figure 5:** Changes in soil and root-associated fungal communities under different fertilization
801 strategies (AS and NC treatments) in 2023 across tillering, elongation, and flowering stages. a) Soil
802 fungal alpha diversity represented by the Chao1 index (species richness) and the Shannon index
803 (species diversity) across tillering, elongation, and flowering stages. b) Venn diagrams illustrating
804 the shared and unique soil OTUs across treatments during these stages. c) Root-associated
805 fungal alpha diversity represented by the Chao1 index and the Shannon index over elongation, and
806 flowering stages. d) Venn diagrams illustrating the shared and unique root-associated OTUs
807 across treatments during these stages. e) Abundance of AMF communities at the root level
808 quantified using the qPCR method during these stages. AS = Ammonium (blue) ; NC = Nitrate
809 (orange).

810

811 **Table 1:** Mean and standard deviation of grain yield ($T ha^{-1}$) for referent varieties and fertilizer
 812 types, analyzed by year and nitrogen application rate. Different superscript letters along the
 813 values for each variety and fertilization indicate significant differences between grain yield.
 814 ANOVA results are provided for the effect of the genotype on yields.

Variety	Treatment	180 uN.ha ⁻¹ (2022)	120 uN.ha ⁻¹ (2023)	120 uN.ha ⁻¹ (2024)	180 uN.ha ⁻¹ (2024)
Cellule	AS	10.835 ± 0.279 ^a	11.014 ± 0.385 ^a	3.613 ± 0.197 ^a	2.964 ± 0.396 ^a
	AN	10.140 ± 0.457 ^b	10.326 ± 0.915 ^a	3.945 ± 0.511 ^a	2.632 ± 0.462 ^a
	NC	10.930 ± 0.437 ^a	10.463 ± 0.785 ^a	4.226 ± 0.580 ^a	2.410 ± 0.551 ^a
Boisseau	AS	10.781 ± 0.382 ^a	10.114 ± 0.258 ^a	4.186 ± 0.355 ^a	3.615 ± 0.534 ^a
	AN	10.346 ± 0.410 ^a	10.182 ± 0.448 ^a	5.353 ± 0.169 ^b	3.837 ± 0.522 ^b
	NC	10.830 ± 0.173 ^a	9.752 ± 1.100 ^a	5.019 ± 0.238 ^c	3.740 ± 0.369 ^a
KWS Smart	AS	11.072 ± 0.593 ^a	9.397 ± 0.551 ^a	5.572 ± 0.384 ^a	4.474 ± 0.760 ^a
	AN	10.623 ± 0.446 ^a	9.641 ± 0.286 ^a	5.927 ± 0.452 ^a	4.654 ± 0.604 ^a
	NC	11.532 ± 0.183 ^b	9.820 ± 0.376 ^a	6.179 ± 0.497 ^a	4.626 ± 0.582 ^a
Pajero	AS	9.385 ± 0.449 ^a	9.368 ± 0.245 ^a	4.791 ± 0.290 ^a	4.515 ± 0.390 ^a
	AN	9.348 ± 0.444 ^a	9.605 ± 0.173 ^a	5.395 ± 0.202 ^a	4.363 ± 0.475 ^b
	NC	10.137 ± 0.124 ^b	9.265 ± 0.329 ^a	5.472 ± 0.400 ^a	4.266 ± 0.567 ^c
p-values (genotype)		6.47 10 ⁻¹⁰ ***	4.7 10 ⁻⁰⁵ ***	2.56 10 ⁻¹² ***	5.52 10 ⁻¹⁵ ***

815

816 **Table 2:** Mean and standard deviation of straw yield ($T ha^{-1}$) for referent varieties and fertilizer
 817 types analyzed by year and nitrogen application rate. Different superscript letters along the values
 818 for each variety and fertilization indicate significant differences between straw yield. ANOVA
 819 results are provided for the effect of the genotype on yields.

Variety	Treatment	180 uN.ha ⁻¹ (2022)	120 uN.ha ⁻¹ (2023)	120 uN.ha ⁻¹ (2024)	180 uN.ha ⁻¹ (2024)
Cellule	AS	5.050 ± 0.387 ^a	7.238 ± 0.648 ^a	2.964 ± 0.396 ^a	2,978 ± 0,439 ^a
	AN	4.175 ± 0.206 ^b	6.506 ± 1.227 ^a	2.632 ± 0.462 ^a	2,715 ± 0,286 ^a
	NC	5.150 ± 0.311 ^a	6.535 ± 0.718 ^a	2.410 ± 0.551 ^a	3,172 ± 0,897 ^a
Boisseau	AS	4.325 ± 0.150 ^a	7.193 ± 0.248 ^a	3.615 ± 0.534 ^a	4,197 ± 0,719 ^a
	AN	4.425 ± 0.206 ^a	6.813 ± 0.520 ^a	3.837 ± 0.522 ^a	3,809 ± 0,688 ^a

	NC	4.750 ± 0.129 ^a	6.637 ± 1.257 ^a	3.740 ± 0.369 ^a	4,017 ± 0,702 ^a
KWS Smart	AS	5.350 ± 0.387 ^a	6.184 ± 1.008 ^a	4.474 ± 0.760 ^a	4,252 ± 0,676 ^a
	AN	5.775 ± 0.618 ^{ab}	6.418 ± 0.374 ^a	4.654 ± 0.604 ^a	4,626 ± 0,528 ^a
	NC	6.3500 ± 0.580 ^b	6.608 ± 0.172 ^a	4.626 ± 0.582 ^a	5.208 ± 0.392 ^a
Pajero	AS	5.475 ± 0.591 ^a	8.377 ± 0.226 ^a	4.515 ± 0.390 ^a	4.446 ± 0.083 ^a
	AN	5.275 ± 0.544 ^a	8.129 ± 1.202 ^a	4.363 ± 0.475 ^a	4.903 ± 0.551 ^a
	NC	5.550 ± 0.985 ^a	7.895 ± 0.551 ^a	4.266 ± 0.567 ^a	4.612 ± 0.592 ^a
p-values (genotype)		2.3 10 ⁻⁰⁷ ***	2.5 10 ⁻⁰⁵ ***	3.9 10 ⁻¹⁰ ***	1.6 10 ⁻⁰⁸ ***

820

821 **Table 4:** ANOVA results are provided for the effect the fertilizers on alpha diversity indices (Chao1
822 and Shannon) across tillering, elongation, and flowering stages at the soil and root levels.

		p-values (Tillering)	p-values (Elongation)	p-values (Flowering)
Soil	Chao1	0.959	0.720	0.798
	Shannon	0.573	0.064	0.798
Root	Chao1	-	0.189	0.049 *
	Shannon	-	0.866	0.006 **

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827 **Figure S1:** Photographs of the experimental trial a) in June 2022 and b) in May 2024.

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830 **Figure S2:** Meteorological data for each trial. Black lines represent sowing and harvest dates,
831 while red dotted lines indicate nitrogen application dates.

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		AS	AN	NC
Cellule	2023	12,49	13,64	13,52
	2024 - 120 UN	14,78	13,94	13,82
	2024 - 180 UN	14,99	14,82	14,11
Boisseau	2023	10,70	12,45	12,50
	2024 - 120 UN	13,63	12,66	12,60
	2024 - 180 UN	14,09	13,29	13,12
KWS Smart	2023	11,06	12,51	12,29
	2024 - 120 UN	13,02	11,72	11,34
	2024 - 180 UN	12,93	12,29	11,95
Pajero	2023	13,45	15,30	14,34
	2024 - 120 UN	14,07	13,41	13,68
	2024 - 180 UN	14,79	14,31	13,88

833

834 **Figure S3:** Heat map representing the grain protein content (% of relative weight) for the referent

835 varieties in 2023 and 2024.

836

a)

Soil nitrogen content (%)

b)

Soil nitrate content (kg N ha⁻¹)

c)

Soil nitrate content (kg N ha⁻¹)

838 **Figure S4:** Soil nitrogen forms measurements under different fertilization treatments in 2022 at
839 180 uN.ha⁻¹ and 2024 at 120 or 180 uN ha⁻¹. a) Proportion (%) of soil ammonium (blue) and nitrate
840 (orange) content throughout the season with or without (soil) wheat cultivation in 2022. T1
841 corresponds to the date before the first fertilizer application, while T2 to T4 are after the
842 applications. Cumulative content (kg N ha⁻¹) of soil nitrate at different depths (0-30 cm, 30-60 cm,
843 and 60-90 cm) during the 2024 season : b) at 120 and c) 180 uN.ha⁻¹.

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846 **Figure S5:** Abundance of ammonia-oxidizing microorganisms communities in soil in April, May,
847 and June 2023. a) ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), and b) ammonia-oxidizing archaea (AOA).
848 AS treatment is shown in blue, and NC treatment in orange.

849

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a)

b)

851 **Figure S6:** Nitrous oxide fluxes measurement over the week following nitrogen application on
852 March 22, 2024. a) Photographs of the measurement system in the field. b) Average N₂O fluxes,
853 N₂O fluxes are expressed in grams of nitrogen per hectare per day (g N·ha⁻¹·day⁻¹).

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856 **Figure S7:** Heatmaps depicting differentially abundant genera identified through the Wilcoxon
857 test, highlighting significant changes between treatments in 2023. a) Soil fungal community
858 across tillering, elongation, and flowering stages, and b) root-associated fungal community
859 across elongation, and flowering stages.

860

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861 **Table S1:** Soil elements content and pH of field experiments. Analyses were performed prior to
 862 fertilization.

Years	2022	2023
Phosphorous	13.7 mg.100g ⁻¹ dry soil	16.7 mg.100g ⁻¹ dry soil
Potassium	23 mg.100g ⁻¹ dry soil	30 mg.100g ⁻¹ dry soil
Magnesium	12 mg.100g ⁻¹ dry soil	11 mg.100g ⁻¹ dry soil
Calcium	416 mg.100g ⁻¹ dry soil	239 mg.100g ⁻¹ dry soil
pH (KCl 1N)	7.6	6.7
Organic carbon	15.6 g.kg ⁻¹	15.4 g.kg ⁻¹
Humus	3.1 %	3.1%
Total carbon	15.6 g.kg ⁻¹	15.4 g.kg ⁻¹
Total nitrogen	0.12%	0.11%
C/N	13	14

863

864 **Table S2:** Mean and standard deviation of grain yield (T ha⁻¹) for elite varieties according to
 865 fertilizer types, in 2023 at 120 uN.ha⁻¹. Different superscript letters along the values for each
 866 variety and fertilization indicate significant differences between grain yield.

Variety	Treatment	Grain Yields		
Boisseau	AS	10.951	± 0.514	bcdefg
	NC	11.385	± 0.393	abcdefg
Cellule	AS	11.546	± 0.317	abcdef
	NC	11.732	± 0.403	abcde
Chevignon	AS	11.518	± 0.563	abcdef
	NC	11.566	± 0.158	abcde
Cubitus	AS	12.021	± 0.386	abcd
	NC	12.084	± 0.477	abcd
Geluck	AS	12.189	± 0.085	abcd
	NC	11.839	± 0.318	abcde

Hyking	AS	12.294 ± 0.590	ab
	NC	12.136 ± 1.120	abcd
KWS Extase	AS	12.205 ± 0.340	abc
	NC	11.61 ± 0.427	abcde
KWS Smart	AS	10.876 ± 0.271	cdefg
	NC	10.501 ± 0.303	efg
LG Apollo	AS	10.918 ± 0.789	bcdefg
	NC	11.735 ± 0.414	abcde
LG Character	AS	11.309 ± 0.567	abcdefg
	NC	11.146 ± 0.647	abcdefg
LG Keramik	AS	11.99 ± 0.329	abcd
	NC	11.589 ± 0.409	abcde
LG Skyscraper	AS	12.408 ± 0.219	a
	NC	12.123 ± 0.275	abcd
Pajero	AS	10.138 ± 0.217	g
	NC	10.183 ± 0.459	fg
Positiv	AS	12.232 ± 0.255	abc
	NC	12.133 ± 0.412	abcd
RGT Perkussio	AS	11.887 ± 0.734	abcd
	NC	11.819 ± 0.264	abcde
Spotlight	AS	10.878 ± 0.642	cdefg
	NC	10.812 ± 0.577	defg
SY Admiration	AS	12.373 ± 0.324	a
	NC	11.351 ± 0.397	abcdefg
SY Insitor	AS	11.919 ± 0.493	abcd
	NC	12.521 ± 0.854	a
SY Revolution	AS	12.219 ± 0.329	abc
	NC	11.802 ± 0.603	abcde
Winner	AS	11.811 ± 0.665	abcde
	NC	12.342 ± 0.205	a

867

868 **Table S3:** Mean and standard deviation of N₂O emission peak expressed in grams of nitrogen per
869 hectare per day (g N·ha⁻¹·day⁻¹) for fertilizer types and nitrogen application rate.

	120uN·ha ⁻¹	180 uN·ha ⁻¹
AS	2.602 ± 0.239	1.918 ± 0.066
AN	16.876 ± 0.320	23.226 ± 0.811
NC	17.698 ± 0.500	24.244 ± 0.559

870

871 **Table S4:** ANOVA results are provided for the effect the fertilizers on total bacterial and archaeal,
872 and for the ratios of bacterial *AmoA/16S*, archaeal *AmoA/16S* during April, May and June 2023.

	p-values (April)	p-values (May)	p-values (June)
<i>bacterial 16S</i>	0.618	0.161	0.176
<i>archaeal 16S</i>	0.787	0.780	0.342
Ratio bact <i>AmoA/16S</i>	0.569	0.108	0.250
Ratio arch <i>AmoA/16S</i>	0.423	0.540	0.827

873

874 **Table S5:** Ecological classification of fungal genera that show differential abundance between AS
875 and NC fertilizations determined by the Wilcoxon test.

Fungal Genus	Ecological Attribution
<i>Acremonium</i>	Soil saprotroph, plant endophyte, or opportunistic pathogen
<i>Alternaria</i>	Ubiquitous plant pathogen, saprotroph, allergen source
<i>Apiospora</i>	Plant pathogen or endophyte, associated with cereals and grasses
<i>Arachniotus</i>	Keratinophilic fungus
<i>Arrhenia</i>	Basidiomycete, often associated with bryophytes (mosses)
<i>Arthrographis</i>	Keratinophilic fungus, opportunistic pathogen
<i>Auxarthron</i>	Keratinophilic fungus
<i>Bannoa</i>	Limited information; possibly saprotrophic
<i>Beauveria</i>	Entomopathogen, biocontrol agent
<i>Burgoa</i>	Limited information; possibly saprotrophic
<i>Candida</i>	Yeast, commensal in humans and animals, opportunistic pathogen
<i>Chaetasbolisia</i>	Plant-associated, possible endophyte or pathogen
<i>Chrysosporium</i>	Soil saprotroph, associated with keratin degradation (hair, nails, feathers)
<i>Cirrenalia</i>	Marine fungus, often isolated from submerged wood
<i>Cladosporium</i>	Common airborne mold, plant pathogen, allergen source
<i>Clitopilus</i>	Saprotrophic mushroom
<i>Coprinellus</i>	Saprotrophic mushroom, grows on dung and wood
<i>Crepidotus</i>	Saprotrophic mushroom, decomposer of wood
<i>Debaryomyces</i>	Marine and terrestrial yeast, salt-tolerant, often isolated from food and beverages
<i>Epicoccum</i>	Ubiquitous saprotroph, plant endophyte, and weak pathogen
<i>Eucasphaeria</i>	Limited information; possibly saprotrophic
<i>Exophiala</i>	Black yeast, saprotroph, and opportunistic pathogen
<i>Falciphora</i>	Limited information; plant-associated or saprotrophic
<i>Filobasidium</i>	Yeast, often associated with plants or soil
<i>Fusarium</i>	Plant pathogen, mycotoxin producer
<i>Fusicolla</i>	Plant-associated fungus, often saprotrophic
<i>Fusidium</i>	Plant-associated or saprotrophic
<i>Ganoderma</i>	Wood-decaying fungus, some species used medicinally
<i>Geastrum</i>	Earthstar fungi, saprotrophs in forest litter
<i>Gibellulopsis</i>	Soil fungus, sometimes plant-associated

<i>Gremmenia</i>	Lichen-associated fungus
<i>Hormiactis</i>	Limited information; potentially keratinophilic
<i>Hormographiella</i>	Opportunistic pathogen, sometimes found in decaying vegetation
<i>Hymenoscyphus</i>	Plant pathogen or saprotroph, associated with ash dieback
<i>Hyphodermella</i>	Wood-decaying fungus
<i>Ilyonectria</i>	Plant pathogen, causing root rot in crops
<i>Itersonilia</i>	Plant pathogen and saprotroph, can infect <i>Allium</i> species
<i>Junghuhnia</i>	Wood-decaying fungus (white rot)
<i>Kregervanrija</i>	Yeast, often found in extreme environments
<i>Leucothecium</i>	Limited information; possibly saprotrophic
<i>Malassezia</i>	Lipophilic yeast, commensal and opportunistic pathogen on animal skin
<i>Malbranchea</i>	Keratinophilic fungus, saprotroph
<i>Melastiza</i>	Saprotrophic, found in soil or decaying matter
<i>Mortierella</i>	Soil saprotroph, often found in rhizosphere
<i>Mrakia</i>	Cold-tolerant yeast, found in polar and alpine environments
<i>Neopyrenochaeta</i>	Plant-associated, possible pathogen
<i>Niesslia</i>	Plant-associated or saprotrophic
<i>Nigrograna</i>	Plant-associated, possible endophyte
<i>Paecilomyces</i>	Soil saprotroph, entomopathogen, also found in decaying vegetation
<i>Papiliotrema</i>	Yeast, often found in plant and soil environments
<i>Periconia</i>	Soil saprotroph and plant endophyte
<i>Phaeochloridium</i>	Plant endophyte, sometimes associated with disease
<i>Phaeosphaeria</i>	Plant pathogen or endophyte
<i>Phialophora</i>	Soil and plant-associated fungi, sometimes opportunistic pathogens in humans
<i>Podila</i>	Limited information; potentially saprotrophic
<i>Podospora</i>	Coprophilous (dung-loving) fungus
<i>Pseudeurotium</i>	Soil and plant-associated fungus, psychrophilic
<i>Rhexocercosporidium</i>	Plant pathogen
<i>Saccharomycopsis</i>	Yeast, found in fermented foods and sugary substrates
<i>Sanchytrium</i>	Limited information; possibly aquatic
<i>Solicoccozyma</i>	Yeast, found in terrestrial and aquatic habitats
<i>Stachybotrys</i>	Saprotroph, commonly found on water-damaged materials, some species toxic
<i>Symmetrospora</i>	Yeast, often associated with aquatic or terrestrial habitats
<i>Tetragoniomyces</i>	Limited information; possibly saprotrophic
<i>Thelonectria</i>	Plant pathogen
<i>Tricellula</i>	Limited information; possibly saprotrophic
<i>Trichoderma</i>	Soil saprotroph, biocontrol agent, plant symbiont
<i>Trichosporiella</i>	Limited information; possibly saprotrophic
<i>Udeniozyma</i>	Yeast, found in terrestrial and aquatic habitats
<i>Unguiculariopsis</i>	Lichen-associated fungus
<i>Vishniacozyma</i>	Yeast, found in extreme environments such as polar regions
<i>Wardomyces</i>	Aquatic fungus, often found in waterlogged wood

877 **Table S6:** ANOVA results are provided for the effect the fertilizers on *Glomeromycota* genera
 878 during the flowering phase in 2023.

Genera	p-values
<i>Ambispora</i>	0.170
<i>Archaeospora</i>	0.441
<i>Claroideoglosum</i>	0.451
<i>Diversispora</i>	0.187
<i>Dominikia</i>	0.488
<i>Funneliformis</i>	0.278
<i>Pacispora</i>	0.144
<i>Paraglosum</i>	0.381
<i>Scutellospora</i>	0.537
<i>Unclassified</i>	0.959

879

880 **Table S7:** Primers list used in this study.

Target	Primer	Sequence (5' -> 3')	Condition if used in qPCR	Source																																			
Archaeal 16S rRNA	771F	ACGGTGAGGGATGAAAGCT	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 60°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Ochsenreiter et al.. 2003																																			
	957R	CGGCGTTGACTCCAATTG			Bacterial 16S rRNA	341F	CCTACGGGAGGCAGCAG	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 63°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Klindworth et al.. 2013 Walker et al.. 2015	534R	ATTACCGCGGCTGCTGGCA	Archaeal <i>amoA</i> (AOA)	amo19F	ATGGTCTGGCTWAGACG	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 60°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Leininger et al.. 2006 Nicol et al.. 2008	Crenamo A616r48x R	GCCATCCABCKRTANGTCCA	Bacterial <i>amoA</i> (AOB)	amoA1F amoA2R	GGGGTTTCTACTGGTGGT CCCCTCKGSAAAGCCTTCTTC	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 60°C for 30s. 72°C for 30s	Rotthauwe et al.. 1997	AMF 18S rRNA	AMG1F	ATAGGGATAGTTGGGGCCAT	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 64°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Hewins et al. 2015 Helgason et al. 1998	AM1	GTTTCCCGTAAGGCGCCGAA	Wheat TaTEF1	TaTEF1-S TaTEF1-A	AACAGCCACAGTTTGCCTCAT GGTTGTGGAGACCTTTGCTACT TAC	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 64°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Wei et al. 2021	Eukaryotic ITS2	ITS3	GCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGC	-
Bacterial 16S rRNA	341F	CCTACGGGAGGCAGCAG	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 63°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Klindworth et al.. 2013 Walker et al.. 2015																																			
	534R	ATTACCGCGGCTGCTGGCA			Archaeal <i>amoA</i> (AOA)	amo19F	ATGGTCTGGCTWAGACG	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 60°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Leininger et al.. 2006 Nicol et al.. 2008	Crenamo A616r48x R	GCCATCCABCKRTANGTCCA	Bacterial <i>amoA</i> (AOB)	amoA1F amoA2R	GGGGTTTCTACTGGTGGT CCCCTCKGSAAAGCCTTCTTC	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 60°C for 30s. 72°C for 30s	Rotthauwe et al.. 1997	AMF 18S rRNA	AMG1F	ATAGGGATAGTTGGGGCCAT	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 64°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Hewins et al. 2015 Helgason et al. 1998	AM1	GTTTCCCGTAAGGCGCCGAA	Wheat TaTEF1	TaTEF1-S TaTEF1-A	AACAGCCACAGTTTGCCTCAT GGTTGTGGAGACCTTTGCTACT TAC	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 64°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Wei et al. 2021	Eukaryotic ITS2	ITS3	GCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGC	-	White et al.. 1990	ITS4	TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC				
Archaeal <i>amoA</i> (AOA)	amo19F	ATGGTCTGGCTWAGACG	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 60°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Leininger et al.. 2006 Nicol et al.. 2008																																			
	Crenamo A616r48x R	GCCATCCABCKRTANGTCCA			Bacterial <i>amoA</i> (AOB)	amoA1F amoA2R	GGGGTTTCTACTGGTGGT CCCCTCKGSAAAGCCTTCTTC	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 60°C for 30s. 72°C for 30s	Rotthauwe et al.. 1997	AMF 18S rRNA	AMG1F	ATAGGGATAGTTGGGGCCAT	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 64°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Hewins et al. 2015 Helgason et al. 1998	AM1	GTTTCCCGTAAGGCGCCGAA	Wheat TaTEF1	TaTEF1-S TaTEF1-A	AACAGCCACAGTTTGCCTCAT GGTTGTGGAGACCTTTGCTACT TAC	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 64°C for 30s. 72°C for 40s	Wei et al. 2021	Eukaryotic ITS2	ITS3	GCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGC	-	White et al.. 1990	ITS4	TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC											
Bacterial <i>amoA</i> (AOB)	amoA1F amoA2R	GGGGTTTCTACTGGTGGT CCCCTCKGSAAAGCCTTCTTC	95°C 5min. 40 cycles of 95°C for 30s. 60°C for 30s. 72°C for 30s	Rotthauwe et al.. 1997																																			
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Eukaryotic ITS2	ITS3	GCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGC	-	White et al.. 1990																																			
	ITS4	TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC																																					

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